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DYNAMIC ROUTE OPTIMISATION IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAINS USING THE ANT COLONY ALGORITHM

Abstract. The study considers the application of the ant colony algorithm for dynamic route optimization in logistics systems to improve supply chain management efficiency. The problem's relevance is due to the need to respond quickly to changing transportation conditions, minimize costs, and ensure the stability of delivery processes. The ant colony algorithm uses the principles of self-organization and collective search for optimal solutions, which allows dynamic changes in transport infrastructure and logistics constraints to be taken into account.

The study aims to develop an approach to building adaptive routes based on the ant colony algorithm to increase the flexibility and efficiency of logistics operations. The research methodology includes mathematical routing modeling and analysis of scenarios for the functioning of logistics systems under different environmental conditions. The model parameters are analyzed to determine their impact on the time required to find the optimal route and the algorithm's resilience to environmental changes.

The study considers such key parameters as pheromone intensity, heuristic evaluation influence coefficients, and pheromone evaporation rate.

The study results show that the algorithm effectively redirects routes in the event of changes in road conditions and avoids congested sections of the transport network. The key implementation problems were found to be high computational costs and the need to integrate the algorithm with information systems to obtain up-to-date data in real time. Successful integration of the algorithm depends on the availability of an infrastructure capable of ensuring the uninterrupted flow of information and its processing.

Recommendations on adjusting the algorithm's parameters in accordance with the logistics network's specifics and using cloud computing to improve system performance are proposed. Prospects for further research include creating hybrid algorithms that combine ant colony methods with machine learning to increase the adaptability and accuracy of forecasts in crisis situations.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, operations research, optimization methods.

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ДИНАМІЧНА ОПТИМІЗАЦІЯ МАРШРУТІВ У ЛОГІСТИЦІ ТА ЛАНЦЮГАХ ПОСТАЧАННЯ З ВИКОРИСТАННЯМ АЛГОРИТМУ МУРАШИНОЇ КОЛОНІЇ

Анотація. У дослідженні розглянуто застосування алгоритму мурашиної колонії для динамічної оптимізації маршрутів у логістичних системах, зосереджуючись на підвищенні ефективності управління ланцюгами постачання. Актуальність проблеми визначається необхідністю швидкого реагування на змінні умови транспортування, мінімізації витрат та забезпечення стабільності процесів доставки. Алгоритм мурашиної колонії ґрунтується на принципах самоорганізації та колективного пошуку оптимальних рішень, що забезпечує врахування динамічних змін у транспортній інфраструктурі та логістичних обмеженнях.

Мета дослідження – аналіз підходу до побудови адаптивних маршрутів на основі алгоритму мурашиної колонії для забезпечення гнучкості та підвищення ефективності логістичних операцій.

Методологія дослідження включає математичне моделювання маршрутів і аналіз сценаріїв функціонування логістичних систем за різних умов середовища. Здійснено аналіз параметрів моделі для оцінки їх впливу на швидкість пошуку оптимального маршруту та стійкість алгоритму до змін середовища. Розглянуто ключові параметри, зокрема інтенсивність феромону, коефіцієнти евристичної оцінки та швидкість випаровування феромону.

Результати дослідження продемонстрували, що алгоритм сприяє ефективному перенаправленню маршрутів у разі змін дорожніх умов і дозволяє уникати перевантажених ділянок транспортної мережі. Основними проблемами впровадження є високі обчислювальні витрати та необхідність інтеграції алгоритму з інформаційними системами для забезпечення актуальних даних у реальному часі. Успішність інтеграції залежить від наявності інфраструктури, здатної забезпечити безперебійне надходження інформації та її обробку. Для підвищення ефективності алгоритму запропоновано адаптацію його параметрів відповідно до специфіки логістичної мережі. Використання хмарних обчислень рекомендовано для оптимізації продуктивності системи.

Перспективи подальших досліджень полягають у розробці гібридних алгоритмів, що поєднують методи мурашиної колонії з машинним навчанням для підвищення адаптивності та точності прогнозів, зокрема в умовах кризових ситуацій. Додаткову увагу слід приділити розробці та тестуванню

алгоритмів в реальних умовах логістичних процесів, оцінці їх практичної ефективності та вдосконаленню моделей інтеграції.

Ключові слова: штучний інтелект, дослідження операцій, методи оптимізації.

Problem statement. Route optimization in logistics and supply chain management is one of the key challenges of modern transport systems, driven by the need to respond quickly to changes in traffic conditions, reduce costs, and ensure supply stability. Dynamic changes, such as traffic congestion, weather conditions, emergencies, and unpredictable delays, require efficient algorithms to find optimal solutions in real time. Traditional route optimization approaches often face limitations due to the excessive number of parameters to process, which complicates decision-making and increases time costs.

Ant colony algorithms offer a promising approach to solving these problems. They model the behavior of natural systems and demonstrate the ability to find optimal paths through collective learning and gradual adaptation to external changes. This approach ensures that routes are self-organizing, taking into account current conditions, which increases the efficiency of logistics systems, reduces the number of empty flights, and promotes the rational use of transport resources.

The study's scientific significance lies in improving existing methods of dynamic route planning, which will increase the accuracy of forecasting and adaptability of solutions in various delivery scenarios. The practical significance lies in the possibility of integrating the proposed solutions into supply management systems to reduce logistics costs and improve customer service, which is especially important in unstable market conditions and limited resources. Thus, the study aims to develop an optimization model that can function effectively in a multifactorial environment.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Dynamic route optimization in logistics systems using the ant colony algorithm is a promising area for improving supply chain efficiency. However, studies show that processing large data streams in real-time and adapting models to changing conditions remain challenging. In turn, the work of X. Zhang demonstrates how a hybrid ant colony algorithm can optimize cold supply chains, ensuring efficient distribution of goods and reducing delivery time [2]. This is complemented by the results of L. Tan, where a modified algorithm helps to avoid congestion in urban networks by taking into account different types of cargo [3].

An important component of dynamic logistics is electric transport, the routing of which L. Fan studies. The proposed ant colony algorithm takes into account the restrictions on charging time, which allows adapting routes to the specifics of electric vehicles [4]. S. Xue considers another scenario—multi-deposit crowdsourcing systems with time windows. Due to the adaptability of the ant colony

algorithm, it was possible to increase the efficiency of processing deliveries with many intermediate points [5].

In production zones, Y. Chen proposes integrating the ant colony algorithm with deep learning methods, which ensures the synchronization of autonomous transport and reduces inter-stage delays [6]. This idea is complemented by the study of Y. Zhang, where the ant colony algorithm is used to optimize the problem of cargo distribution in logistics centers [7]. In the context of construction logistics systems, J. Li proposes using the ant colony algorithm to synchronize the delivery routes of modules while meeting time constraints [8].

The aspect of eco-friendly routing is revealed in the work of Y. Li, where the ant colony algorithm is adapted to minimize CO₂ emissions, making supply chains more “green” [9]. At the same time, L. Wang shows that the combination of the ant colony algorithm and neural networks allows scaling models to serve a large number of customers [10]. H. Wang presented a model for simultaneous loading and delivery of goods in multi-level networks [11].

To avoid stagnant routes in large networks, Y. Su proposed a method to increase the diversity of pheromone traces, which makes the algorithm more resistant to environmental changes [12]. The study of Y. Wang demonstrates the effectiveness of the ant colony algorithm in coordinating inventory and delivery in large logistics companies [13]. J. Chen used a combination of the ant colony algorithm and tabu search to select the best routes in fresh produce transportation systems [14]. The analysis is completed by H. Wu and Y. Gao, where a local search approach allows simultaneous optimization of delivery and pickup of goods with time constraints [15].

Thus, the research confirms the high efficiency of the ant colony algorithm for solving multi-criteria logistics problems. Despite the achievements in route optimization, the issue of adapting models to real-world conditions remains unresolved. The interconnection of supply chain stages and the complex impact of key factors such as logistics priorities and node constraints have not been sufficiently studied. The ant colony algorithm needs to be improved due to its high computational costs, parameter settings complexity, and real-time big data processing data.

Solving these problems will help increase logistics systems' adaptability and stability. The proposed research focuses on developing a model with optimized parameters, integrating the algorithm with information platforms, and using cloud computing to speed up data processing.

The purpose of the article: The article aims to develop approaches to the dynamic optimization of routes in the supply chain system using the ant colony algorithm to improve the efficiency of logistics operations.

To achieve this goal, the following objectives were set:

1. Describe the structure of the supply chain and identify the key factors that influence the effectiveness of route design, including key milestones, logistics priorities, predictable changes, and the optimization objective function.

2. To develop a mathematical model for dynamic route planning based on the ant colony algorithm, which takes into account variable environmental conditions and minimizes computational costs by providing integration with information platforms for processing large data streams in real time.

3. To formulate recommendations for improving logistics systems' efficiency based on modeling results, taking into account the problems of setting algorithm parameters and practical integration into logistics processes.

Summary of the main material. The supply chain is a complex system of interconnected processes that covers all stages of the movement of goods from the supplier of raw materials to the end consumer. The main functions of this system are to ensure uninterrupted transportation, product safety, and timely delivery in accordance with market requirements. Route optimization plays a crucial role in maintaining the efficiency of this process, as it reduces transportation costs, minimizes the time goods spend in transit and improves customer service. In today's dynamic market, transport logistics faces numerous challenges, such as changing demand, congestion, weather conditions, and other unpredictable factors. That is why building optimal routes is a critical aspect of supply chain management (Table 1).

Table 1.

Stages of the supply chain and the role of route optimization in ensuring the efficiency of logistics processes

Stages of the supply chain	Process description	The role of route optimisation
Supply of raw materials	Procurement and delivery of the necessary materials from the supplier to the manufacturer	Minimizing delivery costs and ensuring the continuity of the production cycle
Production	Material processing and manufacturing of finished products	Reduced logistics costs due to optimal vehicle allocation
Warehousing and storage	Placement and management of inventory in intermediate warehouses	Increase the efficiency of internal logistics to avoid excessive costs
Distribution and transport	Delivery of products to points of sale or directly to consumers	Ensure on-time delivery and minimise downtime in the chain
Reverse logistics	Handling returns, redistribution of goods, or disposal	Optimising routes for product returns at no extra cost

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of [1; 2; 3].

In practical terms, each stage of the supply chain plays a key role in ensuring the stability of logistics processes. At the stage of raw material supply, route optimization helps to avoid delays due to excessive load on the main transport routes

and effectively plans the use of resources in the event of changes in demand or force majeure [2]. For example, using optimization algorithms helps identify alternative routes when routes are temporarily unavailable due to road works or weather conditions.

The production stage involves the timely receipt of materials, as any disruption to the delivery schedule can lead to production line downtime and increased overall costs. Optimized routes reduce the risk of overloading warehouses and prevent the accumulation of excess inventory, which avoids unnecessary storage and handling costs.

Internal logistics is key at the warehousing and storage stage. Optimizing transport routes between warehouses and production sites helps speed up processing cycles and reduce equipment downtime. For example, large logistics complexes use automated systems that, through dynamic planning, determine the shortest route for processing batches of goods.

Distributing and transporting the final product depends on efficient route planning that considers delivery time windows, customer requirements, and the need to avoid congested areas. Modern logistics operators use flexible algorithms that allow them to change routes in real-time, for example, when they receive information about accidents or traffic jams. This ensures timely delivery and maintains a high level of customer service.

Reverse logistics also requires optimized routes, as returns, stock redistribution, or disposal can generate high costs if not planned effectively. For example, optimized routes allow returns to be collected from multiple locations in one flight, which reduces fuel costs and processing time. In times of crisis, when the supply chain is under additional strain, such solutions help maintain the stability of the logistics system and ensure its flexibility [9].

The effectiveness of routing in the logistics and supply chain system is determined by a combination of external and internal factors that affect each stage of the delivery process. Key factors include resources available for logistics operations, transport infrastructure conditions, and changes in supply and demand. Logistics priorities are important in determining strategic planning directions: minimizing delivery time, reducing costs, or increasing flexibility in changing demand. Particularly important are parameters that characterize the existence of constraints in the form of delivery time windows, limited transport capacity, or route features. Predictable changes, such as fluctuations in fuel costs, weather conditions, or seasonality, also affect planning efficiency and require a dynamic optimization approach.

The logistics system uses an optimization objective function that defines the criteria for selecting the optimal route. It usually aims to minimize total costs or maximize delivery speed, considering constraints such as several intermediate points and congestion at transport hubs. The correct choice of optimization parameters and

consideration of predicted changes allow the system to remain stable even under conditions of increased uncertainty (Table 2).

Table 2.

The main factors influencing the efficiency of route planning in logistics systems

Factor	Description of the impact on route optimization	An example of a practical application
Logistics priorities	Determine the primary goal of route planning: minimizing costs and time or improving reliability	Express delivery companies prioritize delivery time, even at higher costs
Resource constraints	Includes a number of available vehicles, drivers, fuel, and load capacity	In times of crisis, optimization takes into account the reduction in the number of flights due to a lack of resources
Projected changes	Covers changes in fuel prices, seasonal fluctuations in demand, weather conditions	During holiday demand peaks, companies optimize routes to deliver a large number of orders
Time windows	Limit the arrival time of vehicles to specific points defined by the service schedule	Stores with fixed opening hours need to be planned around specific hours
Infrastructure limitations	Include road conditions, transport hub capacity, and detour options	In case of bridge or overpass repairs, alternative routes are developed

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of [5; 7; 9; 12].

Logistics systems use automated approaches to consider these factors and parameters in today's environment. For example, logistics operators use machine learning algorithms and monitoring systems to collect data on congestion, weather changes, and season fluctuations to adjust real-time routes. This helps to maintain the flexibility of the route network and avoid downtime. During periods of high traffic, such as major holidays or seasonal sales, optimization based on time windows and logistical priorities ensures that resources are allocated evenly and delivery efficiency is improved. Costs are reduced by routing transport through less congested hubs and using detours to avoid problem areas. Thus, a modern logistics system can effectively adapt to changing external and internal factors, maintaining competitiveness and stability even in volatile market conditions.

A mathematical model for dynamic route planning based on the ant colony algorithm is developed to improve the efficiency of logistics processes in changing environmental conditions. The main goal of this model is to find the optimal route with minimum costs and maximum consideration of external factors, such as road conditions, congestion, projected changes in demand, and the capacity of transport hubs. Unlike traditional methods, which are often based on static data and do not consider current changes in real-time, the ant colony algorithm-based model allows

for adaptive route changes using the principles of self-organization and collective search for optimal solutions.

This model is based on a mathematical description of the behavior of an ant colony, where each “ant” represents a separate route, and information about the quality of the route is accumulated using the “pheromonetrail” mechanism. At each step of the algorithm, an ant chooses a route with a certain probability, which is determined by the formula:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{T_{ij} * N_{ij}^{\beta}}{\sum_{K \in AT_{ik}} T_{ik}^{\beta}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- P_{ij} - the probability of an ant moving from point i to point j ;
- $T_{(ij)}$ is the amount of pheromone on edge (i, j) ;
- $N_{(ij)}$ is a heuristic estimate that is inversely proportional to the distance between points;
- α and β - coefficients that determine the influence of pheromone and heuristics, respectively.

After all ants have completed the route, the pheromone is updated:

$$T_{ij}(t + 1) = (1 - \rho) * T_{ij}(t) + \sum_{k=1}^m \Delta T_{ij}^k \quad (2)$$

Where:

- ρ - the evaporation coefficient of the pheromone, which prevents excessive accumulation;
- ΔT_{ij}^k - is the increase in pheromone from the ant k ;
- m - the number of ants in the model.

The optimisation objective function in this model is to minimise the total routing costs:

$$Z = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_{ij} * x_{ij} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- $c_{(ij)}$ is the cost of transportation between points i and j ;
- $x_{(ij)}$ is a variable equal to 1 if the route includes an edge (i, j) and 0 if it does not.

Table 3 shows the main elements of the model and their practical significance for logistics processes.

Table 3.

The main elements of the mathematical model of the ant colony algorithm and their significance in the process of route optimization

Element of a mathematical model	Description	Practical significance
Pheromone intensity parameter	Determines the amount of pheromone left by the ant on the route	Forms priorities when choosing a route
Heuristic function	Takes into account the route length and	Allows to take into account the current state of road infrastructure
Pheromone update function	Detects the addition and evaporation of pheromone	Prevents route stagnation and ensures adaptation to changes
Target function	Optimises transport costs based on constraints	Minimises delivery time and avoids congested areas
Number of iterations	Determines the number of passes of ants along routes	Provides flexibility and accuracy in calculating the optimal route

Source: compiled by the author on the basis of [6; 8; 10; 11; 15].

In today's environment, such a model allows logistics companies to obtain optimal routes even in cases of significant changes in the external environment. For example, the model dynamically selects detours in traffic jams or accidents without interrupting the decision-making process. Thanks to the pheromone evaporation parameters, avoiding over-fixation on one route ensures that new solutions are sought, preventing inefficient detours. Real-time data updates contribute to the efficient allocation of resources and reduce overall transportation costs. Thus, using the ant colony algorithm in dynamic route planning increases the adaptability of logistics systems and maintains a high level of service, which is a key factor in competitiveness.

Implementing the ant colony algorithm in logistics systems is accompanied by several challenges that can limit its effectiveness and require additional solutions to overcome them. One of the main challenges is the high computational cost due to the algorithm's iterative nature, where many ants explore possible routes, and the pheromone trail is updated for each edge of the route. As the number of nodes in the logistics network increases, the computational complexity increases significantly, which can exceed the capabilities of standard hardware, especially when processing data in real-time. This creates the risk of computational delays and unacceptable response times to changes in transport conditions.

Another problem is the complexity of tuning algorithm parameters such as pheromone exposure coefficients (α and β) and evaporation coefficient (ρ). Incorrectly chosen values can cause the algorithm to “stall” when all ants choose the same route without sufficient exploration of alternative paths, or vice versa - excessive exploration delays the optimization process. To increase efficiency, it is necessary to adjust the parameters according to the specifics of the logistics system, type of transport, and amount of data.

Integrating the ant colony algorithm into existing monitoring and management information systems is also an important challenge. Many logistics platforms run on outdated software that does not support processing large data streams in real time [13]. This may require updating software modules and using cloud computing environments that allow the processing of large amounts of data and ensure stable operation even under heavy loads [10]. In addition, integrating the algorithm involves continuously obtaining up-to-date data on the state of the road network, demand, and available resources, which requires additional resources to ensure their relevance and accuracy [5].

To improve the efficiency of logistics systems, when implementing the ant colony algorithm, it is necessary to follow a set of recommendations to optimize the model's performance and eliminate key limitations. First, the model parameters should be carefully tuned, particularly the coefficients and β , which determine the influence of the pheromone and the heuristic function on the route selection. Optimal values of these parameters avoid over-focusing on one solution or over-exploring new routes. In addition, the pheromone evaporation parameter ρ should balance preserving information about previous routes and quickly updating when conditions change.

To process large amounts of data in real-time, it is recommended to use cloud computing platforms that allow distributing computing across multiple nodes and increase system performance [2, 8]. This is especially important for logistics networks with many routes and dynamic changes, where traditional server solutions may not provide the required computing speed. The use of distributed computing minimizes delays and ensures the stability of the algorithm even under peak loads.

Another key step is integrating the ant colony algorithm with traffic monitoring information systems. To adjust routes promptly, it is necessary to continuously exchange up-to-date data on road infrastructure, traffic jams, accidents, and weather conditions. This allows the algorithm to choose the most efficient routes and avoid congested areas, significantly increasing the logistics system's flexibility [14].

It is also important to adapt the algorithm to the specific conditions of the logistics network, considering the type of transport, the volume of orders, and the time constraints on delivery. For example, for urban routes, it is advisable to configure the model to account for restrictions on certain types of vehicles and the availability of detours.

The recommended measures help ensure the stable operation of the ant colony algorithm in complex logistics systems and increase its efficiency by responding quickly to changes in the environment and making optimal use of resources. Further improvements can be made to create hybrid models that combine the ant colony algorithm with machine learning methods to improve forecasting and automatically adjust parameters in real-time.

Conclusions. The study considers the application of the ant colony algorithm for dynamic route optimization in logistics systems. It has been established that the algorithm effectively searches for optimal routes due to the collective interaction of agents and the self-organization mechanism. This allows the model to adaptively respond to changes in road infrastructure conditions and take into account the limitations of the logistics network, making it particularly effective in a highly dynamic environment.

The main problems of implementing the algorithm include high computational costs that increase with the size of the network and the number of iterations, the need to integrate the algorithm with information systems for real-time data processing, and the complexity of adjusting the model parameters to ensure a balance between exploring new routes and using existing solutions.

A set of recommendations is proposed, including adjusting the algorithm coefficients in accordance with the logistics network's specifics, using cloud computing to increase the speed of data processing, and integrating with information monitoring systems to obtain up-to-date information on the state of road infrastructure. These measures help ensure the algorithm's adaptability to changing conditions and minimized delays in decision-making.

Prospects for further research include the development of hybrid algorithms that combine ant colony methods with other approaches, such as machine learning, to automatically adjust model parameters and improve forecasting accuracy. In addition, research is promising to improve the algorithm's stability in the face of large volumes of streaming data and crises in the transport network.

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